

Does cross-pollination occur during seed regeneration at the International Rice Genebank?

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Preserving genetic integrity of accessions through cycles of conservation and regeneration is a major objective of the International Rice Genebank (IRG). The careful management of seed lots at all steps of the conservation-regeneration process contributes to this objective. Although cultivated rice is a self-pollinated crop, cross-pollination between accessions can potentially occur during seed regeneration when numerous accessions usually flower at the same time.

To estimate the outcrossing rate in *Oryza sativa* and determine whether the plot design currently used at IRG for seed regeneration permits outcrossing between accessions, an experiment was conducted at IRRI during the 1996 dry season.

Five pairs of varieties were used (Table 1). All accessions used as the pollen source (male) had a purple-pigmented basal leaf sheath, whereas pollinated (female) accessions had a green basal leaf sheath. Hybrid seedlings showed purple pigmentation. The pollen-receivers represented a large range of variation for stigma length and stigma exertion and the pollinators were matched to the other accessions for plant height and flowering date criteria (Table 1).

Four different planting designs or treatments were studied (Fig. 1). All plots were separated from each other by a 1.5-m-wide alley. Two replications were made for all treatments. The experimental plots were laid out such that pollen sources, especially in treatment T3, were oriented across the predominant direction of the wind (Fig. 1).

Seeds from the female plants were collected from about 50-75 panicles per

treatment per pair of varieties, from which 600-900 good seeds, depending on availability, were germinated for testing.

Varieties BG 90-2, Secano de Brazil, and Red Rice, with an average outcrossing rate across treatments of 0.40%, 0.27%, and 0.35% (Table 2), respectively, were more subjected to outcrossing than Tojo and CI 8898-2 (0.02%) (Fig. 2). These three varieties have longer and more exerted stigmas.

1. Planting designs tested in the experiment (x: male plants, o : female plants).

Table 1. Accessions used in the experiment.

Accession no.	Variety name	Female varieties (green)					Male varieties (purple)				
		Source	Stigma exertion (%)	Stigma length (mm)	Plant height (cm)	Days to 50% flowering	Accession no.	Variety name	Source	Plant height (cm)	Days to 50% flowering
36951	BG 90-2	Sri Lanka	70.8	1.21	133	89	27334	Padi Kawaluhan	Indonesia	141	89
3513	Red Rice	Iran	69.2	1.87	130	80	46747	Tikanathi	India	136	80
3375	Secano de Brazil	El Salvador	68.1	1.88	135	80	58951	Dhanush Ban	Nepal	138	80
2755	Tojo	Japan	35.8	1.00	139	80	2325	Duk Zuk Zodo	Korea	142	80
3432	CI 8898-2	Africa	32.2	1.03	145	80	3441	Mamoriaka	Africa	152	80

Table 2. Average outcrossing rates (%) observed, by entry and treatment.^a

Pollinated accession	T0	T1	T2	T3	Av (by entry)
BG 90-2	0.83	0.50	0.25	0	0.40
Tojo	0.08	0	0	0	0.02
CI 8898-2	0.08	0	0	0	0.02
Secano de Brazil	0.83	0.25	0	0	0.27
Red Rice	0.92	0.50	0	0	0.35

^aSee Fig. 1 for treatment details.

2. Outcrossing rates (%) observed for the different variety × planting design combinations.

The latter trait appeared to be the key trait for the ability to receive exogenous pollen. Treatment T0 was the only one where outcrossing was observed for all varieties; the outcrossing rate was found to be more correlated to stigma exertion ($r = 0.977$, $P = 0.004$) than stigma length ($r = 0.650$, $P = 0.25$). Only BG 90-2, the variety with the most exerted stigma, was cross-pollinated in treatment T2. Outcrossing rate was related to the proximity of male and female plants.

The highest outcrossing rates were observed in T0, where panicles were clipped together (0.08–0.92%). All female varieties showed cross-pollination in this design. The second highest frequency of hybrid seeds was observed in T1, where male and female plants were alternated (0–0.5%). Very few hybrid seeds were observed in T2 (alternate rows). No hybrid was observed in T3 (side-by-side plots).

No outcrossing was observed in T3, which mimics the field design used by the IRG to regenerate seeds. The experiment did not show that outcrossing does not occur during seed regeneration, but it strongly suggested that if outcrossing occurs, it occurs at a rate much lower than the 0.9% observed when panicles are clipped together. Moreover, during normal seed regeneration, seeds are harvested only from the four middle rows out of the eight rows of each plot to decrease the risk of outcrossing. Overall, results did not suggest any need to modify the design for the next regeneration cycles.

Results from T1 showed that seed mixtures can be a significant source of outcrossing and must be avoided. Also, multiplication plots must be carefully monitored to discard plants grown from seeds left from previous experiments.

This study also demonstrated that cross-pollination can occur in farmers' fields where intentional or accidental varietal mixtures are grown, and can contribute to the overall evolutionary process of rice genetic resources. ■

Genetic research

Phylogenetic relationship of genus *Oryza* as revealed by RAPD analysis

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The agronomically important genus *Oryza* L. includes some 20 wild and 2 cultivated species and is divided into four complexes based on morphological and cytogenetical studies. New molecular approaches, such as restriction fragment length polymorphism (RFLP), internal transcribed spacer (ITS) sequencing, random amplified polymorphic DNA (RAPD), and chloroplast sympo sequence repeats (cpSSR), have been increasingly employed to assess phylogenetic relationships of the genus, but controversy still exists with regard to species relationships. This study applied RAPD technology to determine the phylogenetic relationships of *Oryza* and evaluate the value and limitation of this technology in phylogenetic studies.

Total DNA was extracted from fresh or dried leaves of 36 accessions representing 23 *Oryza taxa* and 1 accession from *Porteresia coarctata* and *Leersia hexandra* (see table). Polymerase chain reaction (PCR) RAPD was carried out on a Rapidcycler (ATC) in a volume of 10 μL , containing 1.2 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ primer, 5–10 $\text{ng } \mu\text{L}^{-1}$ genomic DNA template, 50 mmol L^{-1} Tris HCl (pH 8.3), 0.5 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ BSA, 2 mmol L^{-1} MgCl_2 , 0.5U Taq DNA polymerase, 200 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ dNTP, 1% Ficoll, and 1 mmol L^{-1} tartrazine. The first program was two cycles of 1 min at